

Nuclear Fusion Framework for Simulating Universe

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Abstract

Background: Energy and matter is two basic forms of existence in a universe. So, there are two types of interaction in a universe. One is about between energies which takes a form of heat, and the other is about energy and matter which takes a form of work. As of the discussion between energies, interaction could be described. On the other hand, interaction between energy and matter takes another subject. In this paper, symmetrical identicalness would be discussed between these two forms - heat and work.

Methods: By showing mathematical identity of principle between heat and work, law of interaction between energy and matter could be described. Using category theory, way of expression pattern for addressing any reality would be addressed. By using dimensional metric for logical expression, logical structure would be in an expression of number in $\mathbb{R}$. By exemplifying constructing and deconstructing logical structure by basic matrix decomposition methods, explanation for transforming dimensionality by factorizing matrix would be introduced. And identity between heat and work by this mechanism would be shown.

Results: Methods of decomposing matrix could be explained as a basic way of operator that could be adapted to transforming dimensionality. And this transformation gives justification of notation for heat and work.

Conclusions: It could be natural to say there is a universal expression that is consists of numerical ordinals and cardinals. And both heat and work are identical as an expression form of energy and matter. Nuclear fusion could be introduced by simulating universe.

1 Introduction

There is a belief that if one logical expression that applied adequately in reality, the logic expression could be applied identically in the other area of reality. These logic expressions could be interpreted as patterns for interaction between existences.

It can be said that what known as to be dimensionality is a solid expression for constructing reality. And while constructing dimensionality, conversion in one solid expression transforms to another expression which has the same logic meaning, but with different dimensionality. Eventually, logical structure often regulates interactions between existences. This regulation is called as an “interaction” in physics.

Firstly, this paper tries to exemplify application for transforming between logic structure dimensions. There are two aspects of dimensionality of logic structure which is discussed in this paper. One

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is a group of inductive dimensions (mostly what is called as space axis). And the other is a framework that holds the fractional property between the dimensions (mostly what is called as Hausdorff dimension). In this paper, for understanding reality in unique way of approaching logic structure by using Hausdorff dimensionality metric would be introduced. This would give rationale for using numerical methods for approaching nuclear fusion by simulating universe.

Secondly, basic framework of nuclear fusion would be explained in this paper. As for continuing discussion for simulating universe, dimensionality of logic structure is about understanding reality. And making a reliable example out of reality has always been a question. There were many tries for constructing the framework. Most recently, for example, there was a try for understanding the dimensionality taking absolute meaning for a reality, like in Theory of Relativity. In this paper, universe simulated would be introduced to unify four types of energy to understand what is a nuclear fusion.

2 Logical dimensionality

As discussed in Hausdorff dimensionality, notations for logic could be driven like this:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Assuming Hausdorff dimensionality as } \dim, \text{ in Category } \forall C, \\
& \text{if } \exists(\cdot) = TRUE \Rightarrow NAND(\cdot) = NAND(TRUE) = FALSE \\
& \text{if } \exists(\cdot) = FALSE \Rightarrow NAND(\cdot) = NAND(FALSE) = TRUE \\
& \text{Assuming } \dim(NAND(\cdot) = \cdot) = \log 2 / \log 2 = 1, \\
& \dim(NAND(\cdot, \cdot) = \cdot) = \frac{\log 2^2}{\log 2} = 2 \\
& \dim(NAND(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot) = \cdot) = \frac{\log 2^3}{\log 2} = 3 \\
& \dim(NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot), \cdot) = \cdot) = \frac{\log \left(2 \cdot \left(\frac{\log 2^2}{\log 2} \right) \right)}{\log 2} = 2 \\
& \dim(NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot), NAND(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)) = \cdot) = \frac{\log \left(\left(\frac{\log 2^3}{\log 2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\log 2^2}{\log 2} \right) \right)}{\log 2} \\
& \qquad \qquad \qquad = \log_2 6 \approx 2.5849625007
\end{aligned}$$

Following the premises by syllogism, every dimensionality with more than 3 could be minimized in a dimensionality less or equal than 3.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \dim(NAND(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot) = \cdot) = \frac{\log 2^4}{\log 2} = 4 \\
& \equiv \dim(NAND(NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)), \cdot) = \cdot) = \frac{\log (2 \cdot \log 2^3)}{\log 2} = \log_2 6 \\
& \equiv \dim(NAND(NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot)), NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot))) = \cdot) = \frac{\log (\log 2^2 \cdot \log 2^2)}{\log 2} = 2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& e.g. \\
& \dim(NAND(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot) = \cdot) \\
& = \frac{\log 2^5}{\log 2} = 5 \\
& \equiv \dim(NAND(NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)), \cdot, \cdot) = \cdot) \\
& = \frac{\log(2 \cdot 2 \cdot \log_2 2^3)}{\log 2} = \log_2 12 \\
& \equiv \dim(NAND(NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)), NAND(NAND(\cdot, \cdot))) = \cdot) \\
& = \frac{\log(\log_2 2^3 \cdot \log_2 2^2)}{\log 2} = \log_2 6
\end{aligned}$$

As any number larger than 3 could be in form of sum other integers, it's apparent that every logic equation which Hausdorff dimension larger than 3 could be regularized lesser or equal than 3.

More for the premises by syllogism, if proposition takes only one approach between discussion, it becomes proposition for definition. And if proposition takes two approach for completing discussion, it becomes proposition for specification of notion. And lastly if proposition takes full three approach for completing discussion, it becomes proposition for syllogism.

So, it can be said that proposition has types of "definition", "specification", "syllogism" and their combination in every logic complete the intellectual from what has been known as logical. By definition, it is called as deduction.

3 Operations for graph

Broadly speaking, there is a consensus that matrix can be regarded as an expression of a graph. By that mean, so far known as matrix decomposition is a method to construct or deconstruct a graph related to another (at least) two graphs.

If so, what does this two graphs mean? How could its relation be explained?

There are many known matrix decomposition(or factorization) methods in research areas. PCA, SVD, NMF, ICA, and Autoencoder is well-known. For their usage, a few usages have been known:

- As a mean for clustering:
 - Grouping of independent variables by their directions
 - Inclusion or exclusion of independent variables by their contributions
- As a mean for factorization:
 - Direction extraction of independent variables by grouping
 - Contribution extraction of independent variables to set a criteria for inclusion or exclusion

Basically, it's about making a group of independent variables or evaluating the importance of each independent variable when assuming groups of independent variables. So the relation by matrix decomposition could be expressed in like this:

$$X = A \cdot B + E$$

Assume that X is a target, A, B are decomposed matrices, and E is an error term matrix. Note that every decomposition has its error term in order to achieve its decomposition purpose. So, it is clear by what has been known as matrix decomposition makes a target matrix into a product relation of two graphs.

3.1 Matrix decomposition

$$(m \times n) = (m \times a) \cdot (a \times n) + (m \times n)$$

Then, what is the meaning of its derived dimensionality of matrix size? By view of its size identity in matrix product, a is a variable that implies target count of matrix decomposition. If interpreting this term to a graph, it would mean that from originating graph which has m, n size formation, it is possible to create a new relation of graphs of a size commonalities by an at least error term of E . So for example by the decomposition methods, it could be interpreted like this:

- SVD(Singular Value Decomposition) - Decomposition to two graphs with commonalities while minimizing error terms (usually result in relation by most well-grouped result)
- PCA(Principal Component Analysis) - Decomposition to two graphs in commonalities while maximizing covariance between them (usually result in relation by of most commonalities between two graphs)
- ICA(Independent Component Analysis) - Decomposition to two graphs in commonalities while pursuing the most uncorrelated situation for each relation
- NMF(Non-negative Matrix Factorization) - Decomposition to two graphs in commonalities while regulating their result in positive range
- Autoencoder - Decomposition to two graphs in commonalities while clustering input to another

Difference between SVD and PCA in equation is a difference of centering of independent variables, but there is a difference when taking interpretations of the result value. While SVD conserves original value by minimizing an error term, PCA usually done by explaining the commonalities by fitting Gaussian distribution.

ICA generally targets in minimizing correlation. In reality, there is no situation in everything to be fully independent. It's merely resembling of minimizing correlation by 0. So, even though its "independency" can not be established in strict statistical approach, but it's about reality that every correlation could be in minimal correlation.

3.2 Matrix composition

By regularizing deduction discourse in a form of logical syntactic tree, Hausdorff dimensionality itself can said to be have an attribute of cardinality. And since dimension of this chain of log tree is in numerical space $\mathbb{R}$, it's decomposition or composition by using matrix can be justified. So, it can be said that ways of matrix decomposition take a representation of operator which conducts logical decomposition.

- SVD as an operator in logical decomposition - commonalities of logical propositions would be grouped in maximum by their axis-es
- PCA as an operator in logical decomposition - commonalities of logical propositions would be turn out to the other propositions by in percentage of their covariance with sortable order in maximum number of their axis-es

- ICA as an operator in logical decomposition - commonalities of logical propositions that can be set as polarized opposite could be given in maximum number of their axis-es
- NMF as an operator in logical decomposition - commonalities of range of available proposition by in the meaning of other propositions would be given in maximum number of their axis-es

There can be many other operators in an enlightenment of developing other ways of decomposing matrix. And their attributes derived from their own way could give a different meaning of reaching the logic decomposed.

4 Transforming dimensionality

4.1 Rationality vs Irrationality

What is a rationality? What could be perceived as irrational? It's a basic question which eventually becomes a condition for deciding true or false value for a proposition. At least if what can be in a form of logic could be evaluated whether or not it is true or false, how can it be assessed its value's appropriateness?

This appropriateness is usually settled by a given environment in space and time. This ecological view seems to be a relativistic approach, but there is a difference in what is really impeccable truth and what has been truth. So space and time is a critical variable in assessment of the appropriateness of given proposition.

So, how could this appropriateness could be calculated? In general, inappropriateness takes a form of bias. So it becomes an extension of a fallacy. If measurement of the given environment in space and time is to be perplexed, the dimensionality would be in overestimation. On the other hand, if measurement of the given environment in space and time is to be careless, the dimensionality would be in underestimation. So, by filtering the bias in each observation, interactions get stabilized.

4.2 Recognition of spatiotemporal universe

Then how spatiotemporal universe comes to recognition in real world? It is about the context that each state of moment gives. Assuming that each moment of status could be correspond to specific set of dimensionalities with infinity.

$$\text{State } S = (\cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \dots)$$

According to the preceding discussions, every logical proposition corresponds to another decomposable dimensionality. And this leads to the set of infinite state.

$$\text{State } S = (\cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \dots) \Rightarrow \text{State } S = (S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots)$$

Then how can one human recognize a state when there are infinite elements that consists of one state? It can be said that if one can find a best way of describing a state within a finite set of states, the one could recognize a state without any bias.

Then how could this bias be measured and corrected? It could be compared within soundness of the logical composition in itself.

$$\text{Assuming that Optimal State } S^* = (S_1^*, S_2^*, S_3^*, S_4^*, S_5^* \dots, S_n^*)$$

The best description for a single state is a state that converge into a finite set. It's not by the result of pursuing finite description, but by the definition of a best description, finite limitation becomes essential. If finite set could not be derived, the description for the state itself gets the infinite dimensionality and useless in recognition.

Continuing the preceding discussion, every relation between state described as a matrix (graph) could be in a form of dimensionality. Then how this matrix could be perceived? In traditional mathematics a single number has two properties. One is a cardinality and the other is an ordinality. Cardinals have a form of amount, on the other hand ordinals have a form of sequence. This Galois-based approach draws a big picture to the relation between topology and algebra.

4.2.1 Cardinality and ordinality as a whole

Usually, arbitrary number's ordinality is expressed in an integer. It's because set of integer in an available expression is usually an infinite set. But in this paper, optimal state which describes a single state is limited to a finite set. So, expecting ordinality between available element in statements set is quite a natural.

And this leads an arbitrary number's cardinality as a symbol. By measuring cardinality of a symbol, any statement could be converted to closeness between the meaning of the statement. And as a result, cardinality itself is an abstraction of measure between meaning. (e.g. word2vec)

Ordinality in a number usually points out as a process between the statements. For example, by perceiving the sequence between 1 and 3, the cardinal amount itself can tell the difference(2) as a distance between the numbers. But by the ordinality of a number, the process as former and latter gets distinction.

This former and latter relation gets cognitive direction, and as a result, matrix as a relational graph establishes.

As a mean of linguistics, cardinality and ordinality in numbers become whole. Every meaning could become as a regulation between the meanings. And every regulation between the meanings becomes meaning.

4.2.2 Relation from one-to-many and many-to-one in a single number

By the preceding discussion from matrix decomposition, a single number (as a matrix in one-by-one size matrix) could be expressed like this:

$$(1 \times 1) = (1 \times a) \cdot (a \times 1) + (1 \times 1)$$

First of all, it could be said that one single number(cardinality as well as ordinality) forms in as a combination of two vectors. Then, what does this mean in an extension of preceding discussion?

As for in methods for decomposing matrix, number a represents the number of groupings that relation between graphs could have. And by a definition, number a is an integer that has both ordinal and cardinal. These two attributes regulate a definition of set in reality that could be described as a relation represented with conditions of commonalities.

So commonality is an ordinary, and by expansion from ordinary, cardinality establishes.

5 Matter to energy: from fission to fusion

From what has been discussed in an equation of observing reality with CPT relation[1], it could be derived that there are four phases of observation that could be drawn(Table 1).

		Optimal t	With PE	With ME	With OE
Original	(Expectation)	E	Not specific	Not specific	Not specific
Type 1	SR = CR	In symmetry	With T asymmetry	Not specific	Not specific
Type 2	SR - CR > 0	With P, T asymmetry	With P, T asymmetry	With P, T asymmetry	Not specific
Type 3	CR - SR > 0	With C, P, T asymmetry	With C, P, T asymmetry	With C, P, T asymmetry	With C, P, T asymmetry

Table 1: Asymmetry-error relations

$$\begin{aligned}
TEO_{AO,E} &= \sum_n^{N(AO)} LFO(AO, OG_n, F) \cdot TEO_{AO,E} \cdot POD_{AO,OG_n} \\
&\quad \cdot (1 - OE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - PE(E)) \\
Optimal t_{wanted}^* &= \arg \max_t TEO_{AO,E} \\
Optimal t_{actual}^* &= \arg \max_t (TEO_{AO,E} - CR_t + SR_t) \\
&\quad (CR_t > 0, SR_t > 0) \\
\exists E &\Leftrightarrow Optimal t_{actual}^* = \arg \max_t (TEO_{AO,E} - CR_t + SR_t) \approx 0
\end{aligned}$$

Then what is a main point of energy-matter relation to be fused or fission-ed? First of all, let's assume by the equation that energy in matter is realized when error is moderated. So, there could be a two type of realizing energy from matter — fission and fusion.

5.1 Four branches of fusion energy

In this part, four branches of proton-proton process would be discussed.

Basically, energy by fusion is a heat. Heat is about formation of energy which could be transferred to another energy. And by the definition, because four types of energy is correlated in this equation (without any unit notation):

Assuming that, $E_{Electromagnetic} \cdot E_{Gravity} = E_{Weak} + E_{Strong} \models$

$$(Eqn. 1) E_{Electromagnetic} = \frac{E_{Weak} + E_{Strong}}{E_{Gravity}}$$

$$(Eqn. 2) E_{Gravity} = \frac{E_{Weak} + E_{Strong}}{E_{Electromagnetic}}$$

$$(Eqn. 3) E_{Weak} = E_{Electromagnetic} \cdot E_{Gravity} - E_{Strong}$$

$$(Eqn. 4) E_{Strong} = E_{Electromagnetic} \cdot E_{Gravity} - E_{Weak}$$

5.2 Explanation of energies by a fusion

Continuing the preceding discussion, the potential of gravity and electromagnetic energy takes a form of following equation:

$$(Continuing preceding notation) \text{ Assuming that, Time } \exists t, CR_t < SR_t \\ \left(-1 \leq \frac{SR_t - CR_t}{TEO^3} < \frac{1}{TEO^2}\right) \models E_{Gravity} = \frac{SR_t - CR_t}{TEO^3}$$

Assuming that, Time $\exists t$, $CR_t > SR_t$

$$\left(-\frac{1}{TEO^2} < \frac{CR_t - SR_t}{TEO^3} \leq 1\right) \models E_{Electromagnetic} = \frac{CR_t - SR_t}{TEO^3}$$

$$\Rightarrow -2 \leq e^- + e^+ < 1 (\because CR_t - SR_t \leq TEO)$$

By the upper discussion, adding electron and positron causes another two unit minimal state to overcome reality as an energy. And by this energy potential, transferable energy is revealed.

This happens in two ways of fusion. One is to leave two hydrogen ions (Eqn. 1, p-p I branch). And the other is to leave two electrons which in conclusion turns a hydrogen ion to a helium ion and leaves behind gamma ray as electron (Eqn. 2, p-p II branch).

Next, Fusion of strong and weak energy occurs. By of strong energy, it only adds one proton to nuclear and leaves behind one positron and one neutron (Eqn. 3, p-p III branch). It could be perceived as by potentiating strong energy to emit neutron ray, one positron could be derived. By of weak energy, it adds one proton to existing helium and leaves behind one positron and a neutron (Eqn. 4, p-p IV branch). It could be perceived as by potentiating weak energy to emit neutron ray, two atoms fuse by their pulling energy and one positron could be derived.

5.3 Unification of energies for a fusion

So, these four fusion reactions conserves total amount of energy in sum total. And the equation goes like:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Assuming that, } |E_{\text{Electromagnetic}} \cdot E_{\text{Gravity}}| \leq \cos \theta \\
\Rightarrow E &= E_{\text{electromagnetic}} \cdot E_{\text{gravity}} + E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}} \\
&= E_{\text{electromagnetic}} + E_{\text{gravity}} + E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}} \\
&\Rightarrow \text{Electromagnetic Gravitational Field by } \mathcal{B} = \{2, -2, 2i, -2i\} \Rightarrow \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle = \text{Group } G(\cdot) \\
\Rightarrow E &= \frac{E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}}}{E_{\text{Gravity}}} + \frac{E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}}}{E_{\text{Electromagnetic}}} + 2 \cdot E_{\text{Electromagnetic}} \cdot E_{\text{Gravity}} - E_{\text{Strong}} - E_{\text{Weak}} \\
&= (E_{\text{Strong}} + E_{\text{Weak}}) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{E_{\text{Gravity}}} + \frac{1}{E_{\text{Electromagnetic}}} - 1 \right) + 2 \cdot E_{\text{Electromagnetic}} \cdot E_{\text{Gravity}}
\end{aligned}$$

References

- [1] J. Yoon, "General Specification for Simulating Universe," 9 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.techrxiv.org/articles/preprint/General_Specification_for_Simulating_Universe/20704984